

Studies on 6'-hydroxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin

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6'-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin on formylation affords the 5'-formyl derivative and on the Friedel-Crafts acylation the 5'-acetyl derivative, also obtained by the Fries migration of 6'-acetyl derivative. 3'-Methyl benzofurano (6', 7'-8, 7)-4-methylcoumarin has been synthesised from the 5'-acetyl derivative. On the Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and benzylamine 6'-hydroxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin furnishes 2'-H-3'-benzyl-3', 4'-dihydro-1', 3'-benzoxazino-(7', 8'-8, 7)-4-methylcoumarin which has been degraded to 6'-hydroxy-5'-benzylaminomethyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin by heating with HCl. With morpholine it affords 5'-morpholinomethyl derivative.

Robinson and Weygand¹ studied the Pechmann reaction on 6'-hydroxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin.

6'-O-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin has now been subjected to some other reactions with a view to studying the pattern of substitution and to synthesising coumarino- α -and- γ -pyrones and furocoumarins.

On formylation with hexamethylene tetramine, this coumarin afforded the 5'-formyl derivative and on Friedel-Crafts acetylation, the 5'-acetyl derivative which was also obtained on the Fries migration of 6'-acetoxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin. The 5'-acetyl derivative gave colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and a flavone derivative, on Kostanecki Robinson benzylation.

3'-Methyl benzofurano (6', 7'-8, 7'-0)-4-methylcoumarin (I) has now been synthesised by condensation of 6'-hydroxy-5'-acetyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin with bromoacetic ester, hydrolysis of the ester obtained to the corresponding acid and cyclisation and decarboxylation of the acid by heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.

On Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and benzylamine 6'-hydroxy-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin gave a product insoluble in alkali to which the 2'-H-3'-benzyl-3', 4'-dihydro-1', 3'-benzoxazino-(7', 8'-8, 7)-4-methylcoumarin structure (II) has been assigned, on heating with ethanolic HCl the compound afforded 6'-O-hydroxy-5'-benzylaminomethyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin and formaldehyde. The former on Sommelet reaction, afforded 6'-hydroxy-5'-formyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin.

Similarly with aniline the oxazino derivative was obtained but it gave polymeric product on alcoholic hydrolysis. The 2'-H-3'-phenyl-3', 4'-dihydro-1', 3'-benzoxazino-

7', 8'-8, 7-4-methylcoumarin structure has been assigned tentatively to the above compound, on the basis of analytical results.

With morpholine it gave 5'-morpholino methyl derivative and was converted into formyl derivative by heating it with hexamine. Mixed m.p. with 5'-formyl derivative described earlier was not depressed.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

6'-Hydroxy-5'-formyl-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin : 6'-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g. ; 0.01 M) and hexamethylene tetramine (5.62 g. ; 0.04 M) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml.) were heated on a steam bath for 7 hr. Hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) was then added and the heating continued for further 2 hr. The product obtained on extraction with ether, crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 265-67°. It developed an intense reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 68.5 ; H, 3.5. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4 \cdot 1/2 H_2O$ requires C, 68.4 ; H, 3.5%.)

The 2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone : Prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene in needles gave m.p. 295-97° (Found : N, 13.5. $C_{21}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires, N, 12.9%.)

6'-Hydroxy-5'-acetyl-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin : 6'-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g. ; 0.01 M) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.2 g. ; 0.04 M) and acetic anhydride (3 ml.) and heated in an oil bath at 140-50° for 2 hr. The product obtained on heating the reaction mixture with hydrochloric acid crystallised from acetic acid in yellow crystals. M.P. 315-17°. (Found : C, 71.2 ; H, 4.3. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6 ; H, 4.4%.) It gave a bright brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The acetoxy derivative was prepared by refluxing 6'-hydroxy-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g. ; 0.01 M) and acetic anhydride (5 ml. ; 0.05 M) for 2 hr. on a

wire gauze. The product crystallised from acetic acid in white crystals, m.p. 207-09°. (Found : C, 71.5 ; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6 ; H, 4.4%.)

The 5'-acetyl derivative described above was obtained when the acetoxy derivative (2.6 g. ; 0.01 M) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.2 g. ; 0.04 M) and heated at 125° and then slowly to 170° during the period of 2 hr. Dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) was added and the mixture was again heated on a steam bath for 30 minutes. The crude product was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 315-17. Mixed m.p. with the product obtained from Friedel-Crafts acetylation was not depressed.

4-Methyl-3'-benzoyl-flavono-(7', 8'-8, 7)-coumarin : A mixture of 6'-hydroxy-5'-acetyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin (2.68 g. ; 0.01 M), benzoic anhydride (6.6 g. ; 0.03 ; M) and sodium benzoate (2.8 g. ; 0.02 M) was heated for 8 hr. at a temperature of 180-90° in an oil bath. The product crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 311-12°. (Found : C, 78.3 ; H, 4.0. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 78.5 ; H, 3.9%.)

Ethyl 5'-acetyl-6'-(4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarinyl) oxyacetate : (6'-Hydroxy-5'-acetyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g. ; 0.01 M), bromoacetic ester (1.6 g. ; 0.01 M), and potassium carbonate (1.3 g. ; 0.01 M) were refluxed in acetone for 4 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 138-39°. (Found : C, 67.8 ; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 67.7 ; H, 5.1%.)

5'-Acetyl-6'-(4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarinyl) oxyacetic acid : The above ester on hydrolysis by heating with sodium hydroxide (5%) on a water bath for one hour gave 5'-acetyl-6'-(4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarinyl) oxyacetic acid which was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 220-22°. (Found : C, 65.9 ; H, 4.0. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 66.2 ; H, 4.3%.)

3'-Methyl benzofurano-(6', 7'-8, 7)-4-methylcoumarin : The above acid (1.5 g.) was heated with sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (3 ml.) on a wire gauze for 45 minutes. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in ice cold water was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 252-53°. (Found, C, 77.8 ; H, 4.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.3 ; H, 4.5%.)

2'-H-3'-benzyl-, 4'-dihydro-1',3'-benzoxazino-(7',-8'-8, 7)-4-methylcoumarin : Formalin (0.6 ml.) was dissolved in alcohol (5 ml.). Benzylamine (1 ml.) was added gradually with cooling followed by 6'-hydroxy 4 methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g.) in alcohol. The reaction mixture was gently refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product went in solution within 10 minutes and then bright shining yellow plates separated out. The product collected after keeping the reaction mixture at the room temperature overnight crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture in needles, m.p. 208-09°. (Found : C, 77.6 ; H, 5.6 ; N, 3.8. $C_{23}H_{19}O_3N$ requires C, 77.3 ; H, 5.3 ; N, 3.9%.)

6'-Hydroxy-5'-benzylaminomethyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin : The above oxazino derivative (1 g.) was refluxed with ethanolic HCl (1 : 1) for 2 hr. and

the product obtained on neutralising with sodium bi-carbonate was crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture in white tufts, m.p. 160°. (Found : C, 76.4 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 3.8. $C_{22}H_{19}O_3N$ requires C, 76.5 ; H, 5.5 ; N, 4.0%).

2'-H-3'-phenyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-benzoxazino-(7',8'-8,7)-4-methylcoumarin : 6'-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g.), aniline (1 ml.) and formalin (0.7 ml.) were dissolved in ethanol (15 ml.) and refluxed for 2 hr. on a water bath. The product separated was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 201-02°. (Found : C, 77.5 ; H, 4.9 ; N, 3.9. $C_{22}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 77.0 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 4.0%).

On hydrolysis the above base gave a polymeric product insoluble in all organic solvents and very high melting.

6'-Hydroxy-5'-morpholinomethyl-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin : A mixture of formalin (0.3 g.), morpholine (0.87 g.) and 6'-hydroxy-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (2.6 g.) was refluxed in alcohol (5 ml.) on a water bath for 2 hr. The mixture gets clear after ten minutes and the product separated recrystallised from benzene-petrol mixture as white plates, m.p. 200°. (Found : C, 69.9 ; H, 5.5 ; N, 4.1. $C_{19}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 70.1 ; H, 5.9 ; N, 4.3%).

The above Mannich base (2.6 g.) and hexamethylene-tetramine (5.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid were heated for 6 hr. on a steam bath and then HCl (con. 15 ml.) was added and the heating continued for 2 hr. The product obtained on ether extraction crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 265-66°. Mixed m.p. with 6'-hydroxy-5'-formyl-4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin described earlier was not depressed.

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